

wimby
WIND IN MY BACKYARD

WIMBY – Wind In My BackYard:

**Using holistic modelling tools
to advance social awareness
and engagement on large wind
power installations in the EU.**

Short Overview

The WIMBY project goal is to support the adoption and acceptance of wind-power in the European Union by addressing challenges that threaten its deployment and developing innovative tools to facilitate citizen and stakeholders interaction, knowledge sharing, and collaborative evaluation of impacts.

Methodology

Identify and assess the concerns and impacts from social, health, and environmental perspectives

Identify who are the different actors affected

Identify trade-offs and synergies between impacts to create deployment strategies

Apply Citizen Science and Social research methodologies to involve local stakeholders in decision-making processes

Objectives

#01 To evaluate the impacts on biodiversity (terrestrial and marine fauna).

#02 To evaluate wind farms affects local communities and address issues concerning governance, regulation, health, safety, and landscape impacts.

#03: To identify the best areas for wind power farms deployment and develop methods to foster social acceptance.

#04: To validate modelling tools and develop guidelines to deliver clear overviews of the cumulative impacts of wind installations.

#05: To develop a Web-GIS interactive forum where stakeholders and local communities can exchange information to support the planning of new wind parks.

#06: To build an immersive 3D environment that allows stakeholders to better understand the impacts and the trade-offs of wind energy development.

#07: To develop a framework for wind farm planning, which will include guidelines for participatory processes extrapolated from the forum.

Concept image

- EXISTING MODELS AND DATASETS
- NEW OR UPDATED MODELS AND DATASETS
- LAYOUT AND COST OPTIMIZATION TOOL

Contacts:

Project coordinator

Thierry Coosemans | Vrije Universiteit Brussels
coordinatorteam@wimby.eu

Scientific coordinator

Luis Ramirez Camargo | Utrecht University
l.e.ramirezcamargo@uu.nl

Dissemination leader

Rebecca Huetting | Deep Blue Italy
rebecca.huetting@dblue.it

 [wimby_project](#)

 [WIMBY - Wind In My BackYard](#)

General information:

info@wimby.eu

www.wimby.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's research and innovation programme Horizon Europe under the grant agreement No. 101083460.

Consortium:

